
Environmental Influence and Workplace Bullying as Correlates of Teacher Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria

Awonegan Folayira Ireola (PhD)¹, Prof. (Mrs) O.A Adegun²

¹Department of Educational Management & Business Studies Federal University Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

²Department of Educational Management Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Teacher job performance is fundamental to the effective functioning of educational systems and the improvement of teaching and learning outcomes. However, in Southwest Nigeria, teacher job performance has become a significant challenge due to workplace challenges and environmental influences. This study examines Environmental Influence and Workplace Bullying as Correlates of Teacher Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria. Specifically, it investigates the prevalence of workplace bullying, the extent of environmental influence, and their combined effects on teacher job performance. The research adopts a descriptive survey design, focusing on a sample of 1,575 participants, comprising 1,500 teachers and 75 principals across public secondary schools in Southwest Nigeria. The multistage sampling method, which incorporates simple random sampling and proportionate random sampling techniques, was used to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using three standardized instruments: Workplace Bullying Questionnaire (WPQ), Environmental Influence Questionnaire (EIQ), and Teacher Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ).

Results revealed a significant negative relationship between workplace bullying and teacher job performance, with workplace bullying being prevalent in many schools. Teachers who experienced bullying exhibited lower levels of job satisfaction, motivation, and overall performance. Conversely, environmental influence was less prevalent but still contributed to teacher performance in specific contexts. The study found that the joint effect of workplace bullying and environmental factors significantly impacted teacher job performance, with performance levels rated as moderate overall. Further analysis highlighted those environmental factors, such as school location near markets, industrial areas, and noisy environments, created distractions that hindered optimal teacher performance. Additionally, the lack of protective policies to address workplace bullying aggravated the problem. Teachers frequently faced verbal abuse, threats, and intimidation from colleagues, administrators, and even students, fostering a hostile work environment.

The study underscores the critical need for proactive measures to address workplace bullying and environmental challenges in public secondary schools. Policy recommendations include the enforcement of anti-bullying regulations, the establishment of clear reporting and grievance mechanisms, and improved school placement policies to ensure a conducive teaching environment. Furthermore, capacity-building programs for principals and teachers on workplace ethics and conflict resolution are vital to promoting harmonious working relationships. Stakeholders, including policymakers, school administrators, and community leaders, must collaborate to create secure and supportive school environments that enhance teacher effectiveness so that the education system in Southwest Nigeria can achieve higher teacher job satisfaction and improved teaching and learning outcomes. Ultimately, reducing workplace bullying and mitigating environmental challenges are essential steps toward fostering a sustainable and high-performing educational system.

KEYWORDS: Teacher Job Performance, Workplace Bullying, Environmental Influence, Public Secondary Schools.

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INTRODUCTION

In building a nation, education is of a great importance to both the citizens and government. The purpose of education is to equip the citizenry, to reshape the society and eliminate inequality. Education forms the basis of literacy, skills acquisition and technological advancement. Adegun (2013) asserts that the key to national development and modernization is education.

In Nigeria, education system is divided into primary, secondary and tertiary levels. Each of these levels of education has teachers who are qualified and work towards actualizing educational goals for each stage of education. Secondary school is the second stage of education in Nigeria. It is a critical stage of educational structure that exists primarily to inculcate desirable knowledge in students. It plays a vital role in creating a country's human resource base at a level higher than primary education (Achoka & Odebero, 2007). This also aptly corroborates the claim by Ajayi, Ekundayo and Osalusi (2010) that secondary school is the next level after the primary level, and it is very essential for the formation of human capital. From this stage, students graduate to tertiary institutions. This stage of education requires competent and reliable teacher

For secondary schools to achieve its goals, it must have effective teaching and learning processes. This includes teachers who can effectively handle every aspect of teaching which includes teaching techniques, interactions with students, teaching behaviours and so on. Teaching is a highly noble profession and of great importance to education. The teacher is a key facilitator of knowledge, and plays a vital role in nation building. A teacher is a person that translates educational philosophy, goals, and objectives, into knowledge and skills and transfers them to students in the classroom. Studies on teacher indices revealed the teacher as the greatest singular factor influencing the teaching learning process. Adegun (2010) and Omotayo (2007). Ozdemir and Yirmibes (2016) opined that teacher job performance is defined as their contribution to the achievement of educational goals and objectives. Some other studies stated that teacher job performance is limited to teaching behaviour (Bashir, Alias, Saleh, & Halizah, 2017; Okeniyi, 1995 cited in Amin 2013). It could also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives (Olaniyan 1999).

Teachers are widely recognized as the fundamental pillars of any educational institution, serving not only as managers of resources but as the primary arbiters of whether set educational objectives are achieved. The quality and effectiveness of an educational system are inexorably linked to the competence and dedication of its teaching workforce. A teacher's job performance is multifaceted, encompassing their subject matter expertise, their efficiency in executing duties, and their ability to foster a learning environment that promotes student comprehension and performance. Teacher job performance is one of the most important aspects of education system and involves pattern of behaviours that produce services for the students (Ozdemir and Goren, 2017).

However, it appears that the educational landscape in Nigeria has been marked by a persistent decline in teacher job performance. This decline is often seen as a reflection of the challenges facing the teaching profession itself. An examination of the state of education in the Southwest region of Nigeria suggests that teachers have underperformed in core responsibilities, such as preparation of lesson notes, mastery of subject matter, supervision of students, use of instructional materials, poor regular assessment of students. This professional inadequacy appears to be significantly detrimental to student learning, highlighting the urgent need to understand and address the factors that influence teacher job performance. In Southwest Nigeria, teacher job performance seems to be a mirage as most of the targeted goals of schools seem not to be met. The present-day teachers are accused of gross inefficiency (Ekundayo, 2009).

It has been observed that one of the indices that hinder teacher job performance is environmental influences around the school premises. Despite the efforts of staff, students, and management in realizing educational goals, it is pathetic that the parlous state of physical environment of schools has remained a serious problem. It seems that students interact with the bad elements in society for instance garage boys who live around the school. It also seems that pupils sneak out during school hours to join bad gangs, which means that some schools are built not too far from gangs, inadequate and conducive office spaces for school teachers, it appears there are no functional potable water in schools for drinking example: standard toilets for male and female teachers. School properties are vandalized by community members after close hours. Adegun (2024) school environment plays a strategic role on teacher's performance. This is because the environment provides infrastructural facilities, good motivation for teachers' instructional materials and school climate to enable teachers perform excellently well. Consequently, lack of enabling environment in secondary schools such as vandalization of infrastructural facilities by community members, or thieves braking into the school to take away the properties of the school. Adegun and Olumoyo (2017) assert that most school facilities are ramshackle. School environments should not be bushy and must be well fenced to guide against intruders stealing office furniture. Security personnel must be deployed to each school to watch over the school facilities, when school environment is conducive, teachers will attend classes regularly and giving their best in order to inculcate knowledge to students and this may eventually lead to effective performance of teachers. Teaching and learning in some places take place under the tree or open spaces. School buildings should be repaired regularly and maintained with inadequate toilet, roofs, fences, play grounds and furniture, this naturally makes the environment conducive for everyone, especially teachers

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It appears that physical facilities are in deplorable state in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The probable reason why physical facilities are in deplorable state is because of the poor maintenance culture. Oyewole and Fadare (2018) mentioned that if these school plants such as generator, computer system, laboratory, classrooms, and all other equipment are well maintained, they will facilitate the teaching and learning process and ensure the achievement of the school's objectives. Classes must be ventilated and there must be functional lighting in the classrooms. Therefore, office design encourages employees to work in a certain way by the way their work stations are built. It was observed that in some schools where their roofs are blown off by rain storm, repairs are not adequately made on time to the extent that those buildings become unusable. When maintenance of physical facilities is delayed or not done on time, it will continue to depreciate and be in deplorable state. Also, more classrooms should be provided for schools where students are more than the infrastructural facilities which has led to overcrowding, which makes teaching and learning process a difficult task to accomplish. In addition, teachers stay under the hot sun to teach students, and classroom roof leaks when there is heavy rainfall. Teachers in such physical facility are not happy with the working environment which leads to poor teacher job performance. Also, windows and doors of a classroom must be in good condition, because students appear to use them as escape route to sneak out of the class room, hence affecting students' performance and that of the teacher indirectly.

It is a known fact that school facilities provided by government are not adequate, but the few that have been provided should be managed appropriately. Also, inadequate and decayed infrastructures should be replaced to promote teacher job performance in secondary schools. Public secondary school seems to face with the challenges of inadequate vocational skills, poor schooling and lacking facilities to cater for pupils. In terms of teaching content, observation shows there is a total discrepancy between the declared policy on education and the provision of teaching facilities and the structural preparation for it. Adegun (2010) emphasized that the quality and quantity of the educational facilities available within the education system have positive relationship with the standard and qualities of that educational system. Consequently, teachers are at the receiving end of the whole problem. Thus, teachers seem to find it difficult to live up to the expectations placed on teaching, because the school environment seems not conducive for both teaching and learning.

School environment plays a strategic role on teacher job performance. This is because when the environment is conducive it makes teaching and learning effective. lack of enabling environment in secondary schools such as vandalization of infrastructural facilities by community members, or thieves breaking into the school to take away the properties of the school, damaging office furniture due to lack of security personnel to watch the school after closing hours, if all these could be eradicated it could lead to effective teaching and learning, and encourage teachers to attend classes regularly.

In Nigeria Tribune, Olatunji and Bajah (2021) reported that the school environment is not safe for teachers and students following the kidnap of the Vice Principal of Yebu Junior Secondary School in Kwali Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory. According to an eyewitness, the kidnappers surrounded the quarters of the staff members while others scaled the fence into the school on Saturday night, and took him away. Teachers living within the school premises appear not safe because of several threats to their lives by kidnappers, and thieves. However, it seems so many teachers are caught up with insecurity which does not only affect their job performance, but their lives and properties.

Bullying can be described as an act of using physical force against a person intentionally which result in harm of the individual's health, survival, development and dignity (World Health Organization, 2014). Bullying is an aggressive and manipulative behavior or series of act by one or more people against one or more people, over a period of time. Bullying is a negative behavior which seems to ravage schools. From observation, it seems that there is no good rapport between teachers because of workplace bullying from some senior colleagues to teachers that are less experienced. Also, workplace bullying appears to occur between some principals and their teachers, which consequently affect their performance in schools. This unpleasant act happens among students, and among teachers, even from principals to teachers and other staffs. It has been observed that female teachers, and teachers with less experience, may experience more of bullying. Students sometimes go to the extent of calling teachers names that appears to be offensive and bad. When bullying is brought under control it will not cause damages to teachers' psychological health, it will improve their self-esteem, stop depression, and they will love to come to work regularly. Teachers are not supposed to be bullied through delaying the payment of salaries. Delaying teachers' opportunity to further their studies, promotion, and in appropriate specific tasks among teachers

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the environmental situation of public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the rate of bulling of teachers in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses are formulated to guide the study.

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1. There is no significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between workplace bullying and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

1. There is no significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools. result

In testing hypothesis six, data obtained on environmental influence and data on teacher job performance were collated and subjected to PPMC at 0.05 significant level. The result is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Relationship between Environmental Influence and Teacher Job Performance

Variables	N	df	r.cal	p-value
Environmental Influence	75	148	0.304*	0.002
Teacher Job Performance	75			

P<0.05

Analysis presented in Table 1 showed that there was significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools. This is because the p-value of 0.002 obtained is less than 0.05 significant level. Hence, the tested hypothesis is hereby rejected. This implied that there is significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools.

The study further revealed that there was a significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest Nigeria. It could be inferred that teacher job performance will be above average if school environmental influence was controlled. The probable reason for this finding might be due to schools located near the market place, when school is sited far away from teachers and students' residence. when there is no conducive space for school teachers, and when properties are vandalized by community members after school hours. The finding aligns with Elizabeth (2022), who revealed that school noise, class room setting and school environment affect students and teacher respectively. It also found out that the school environment must be conducive so that students and teachers can feel relaxed, comfortable, and participate more actively in the teaching and learning-process. Secondly teachers should help in minimizing students' noise and environmental noise while in school. School management could ensure that schools are sited in areas devoid of noise. Adegun (2000) found that the inadequacy of infrastructures affects the effectiveness and commitments of teachers as well as the academic performance of the students. Smit and Plessis (2011) also concluded that a significant relationship existed between work safety and service delivery

2. HYPOTHESIS TWO:

There is no significant relationship between workplace bullying and teacher job performance in public secondary schools. To test the hypothesis, data on workplace bullying and that of teacher job performance were merged and subjected to PPMC at 0.05 level of significance. The result is in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Workplace Bullying and Teacher Job Performance`

Variables	N	df	r.cal	p-value
Workplace Bullying	75	148	0.320*	0.05
Teacher Job Performance	75			

P = 0.05

As presented in Table 6, the relationship between workplace bullying and teacher job performance was significant. This is because the p value obtained is 0.05. Hence, the tested hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between workplace bullying and teacher job performance in public secondary schools is hereby rejected.

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3. What is the level of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Level of Teacher Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools

Variables	\bar{x}	Remark
Students' Supervision	2.75	Moderate
Use of Instructional Materials	2.57	Moderate
Mastery of Subject Matter	2.49	Low
Lesson Planning	2.72	Moderate
Regular Assessment of Students	2.59	Moderate
Grand Mean	2.62	Moderate

Result presented in Table 3 revealed the level of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The level of students' supervision, lesson planning and regular assessment of students was moderate while the level of mastery of subject matter was low. Overall, the grand mean of 2.62 implied a moderate level of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

SUMMARY

This study investigated environmental influence and workplace bullying as correlates of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in southwest, Nigeria. Specifically, the level of teacher job performance in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. Work place bullying is the most prevalent security factor in secondary schools in Southwest.

The level of teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria was moderate while, there was significant relationship between environmental influence and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded teacher job performance effectiveness in Nigeria is connected to good learning environment, and a safe place free of bullying. There should be policy and regulations against workplace bullying, Stakeholders must be deliberate in deploying trained personnel to guard the school premises during the day and night.

Administrators of secondary schools must also be deliberate on the importance of setting up Close Circuit Television (CCTV) at strategic places in the school to monitor activities of students, staffs, and any external intruder into the school at any point in time.

Ministry of education, Teaching Service Commission should organize workshops, seminars, and conferences for teachers from time to time. This will improve their performance and efficiency when discharging their duties.

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ITEM ANALYSIS OF SECURITY MATTERS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

Environmental Influence	SD	D	A	SA	
My school is located near the market place	468 31.2	327 21.8	321 21.4	384 25.4	2.59
The school is sited far away from teachers and students' residence	329 21.9	332 22.1	509 33.9	330 22.0	2.44
School cited beside mechanical workshop distract students' attention.	296 19.7	303 202	435 29.0	466 31.1	2.29
My school is situated in a serene and conducive environment	124 8.3	246 16.4	609 40.6	520 34.7	1.98
Conducive office space is available for the school teachers	156 10.4	227 18.5	571 38.1	495 33.0	2.06
Functional potable water is made available in the school	107 13.1	233 15.5	568 37.9	502 33.5	2.08
Standard Toilets for male and female teachers is available.	160 10.7	197 13.1	591 39.4	550 36.7	1.98
School properties are vandalized by community members after close hours.	293 19.5	277 18.5	444 29.6	483 32.2	2.25
My school has trained security personnel to guard the school premises.	291 19.4	288 19.2	501 33.4	420 28.0	2.30
Teaching activities are affected when the school environment is not conducive	114 7.6	157 10.5	491 32.7	738 49.2	1.76
Bullying					
Teachers bully their junior colleagues.	651 43.8	288 19.2	319 21.3	236 15.7	2.91
Teachers get bullied by the students.	516 34.4	399 26.6	371 24.7	214 14.3	2.81
Teachers experience job threats by the principal.	558 37.2	314 20.9	354 23.6	274 18.3	2.77
Teacher's benefits are sometimes intentionally delayed.	354 23.6	305 20.3	463 30.9	378 25.2	2.42
The school management organises workshop to orientate the teachers on bullying.	313 20.9	360 34.0	510 34.0	312 20.8	2.46
Workplace bullying psychologically affect teachers to deliver effectively.	319 21.3	338 22,5	477 31.8	366 24.4	2.40
The principal put necessary mechanism in place to report any bullying activities.	245 16.3	307 20.5	478 31.9	470 31.3	2.21